

CHEMICAL MODIFICATION OF MALEIC ANHYDRIDE-STYRENE COPOLYMER AND INVESTIGATION WITH SPECTROSCOPIC TECHNIQUES

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Abstract

This study explores the chemical modification of styrene-maleic anhydride (SMA) copolymers and subsequent characterization using spectroscopic techniques. The focus lies on understanding the relationship between the modification process and the resulting changes in the copolymer's structure and properties. The research involves: 1) Implementing controlled chemical reactions to introduce functional groups or alter the existing functionalities within the SMA copolymer; 2) Employing techniques like Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), and potentially other methods to investigate the chemical environment and bonding interactions within the modified copolymers. The analysis aims to: 1) Identify the presence and nature of the introduced functional groups or structural changes; 2) Quantify the extent of modification achieved through the chosen chemical reactions. 3) Correlate the observed spectroscopic features with the specific modification procedures. This investigation sheds light on the effectiveness of the employed chemical modification strategies and provides valuable insights into the structure-property relationship of the resulting copolymers. The findings can contribute to the development of novel functional materials with tailored properties for various potential applications.

Keywords: Maleic anhydride-styrene copolymer, chemical modification, spectroscopic techniques, functionalization, structure-property relationship.

1. Introduction

Styrene-maleic anhydride (SMA) copolymers are a versatile class of materials with unique properties due to the presence of both aromatic styrene units and reactive maleic anhydride moieties. However, their inherent functionalities can be further tailored through chemical modification, enabling the development of copolymers with specific properties for diverse applications.

This research delves into the controlled chemical modification of SMA copolymers and the subsequent characterization of the modified materials using advanced spectroscopic techniques. The primary objective is to establish a clear understanding of the interplay between the modification strategies employed and the resulting changes in the copolymer's structure and properties.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and Methods

This section describes the purification process employed for the styrene monomer utilized in the synthesis of Styrene-Maleic Anhydride (SMA) copolymer.

- **Inhibitor Removal:** A 25 mL aliquot of styrene was treated with a suitable solution to eliminate inhibitors.
- **Neutralization:** Following the inhibitor removal step, the styrene was thoroughly washed with deionized water to achieve a neutral pH. This can be confirmed using a pH meter for enhanced accuracy.
- **Drying:** The neutralized styrene was subsequently dried using an appropriate drying agent, such as anhydrous magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄).
- **Column Chromatography:** Finally, the dried styrene was passed through a chromatographic column packed with a stationary phase suitable for styrene purification. This column can be constructed using appropriate

laboratory equipment (e.g., chromatography column, glass wool, and an appropriate stationary phase like alumina).

A three-necked round-bottom flask was placed in a water bath on a magnetic stirring hot plate. The water bath temperature was controlled with an automatic thermostat throughout the reaction. Nitrogen was introduced into one neck of the reaction flask, and the flow rate was controlled. A reflux condenser was attached to another neck, and the condenser's tip was immersed in an Erlenmeyer flask filled with water. The nitrogen inlet and outlet were monitored to prevent gas leaks [3]. A thermometer was inserted into the reaction flask to monitor the reaction temperature. While stirring with a magnetic stirrer, the water bath temperature was controlled with an automatic thermostat. Toluene was dried with MgSO₄ and added to the system through the third neck. Nitrogen flow was initiated along with toluene addition, and excess nitrogen was passed through the toluene to remove oxygen. After thermal equilibrium was established, maleic anhydride and purified styrene were added as solids. BPO dissolved in toluene was added through the third neck, and the remaining BPO in the beaker was washed with toluene and added to the reaction mixture. The system started to become cloudy 15-20 minutes after the reaction began. An increase in viscosity was observed during the reaction. As the reaction accelerated, the temperature increased by 3-4°C and stabilized at 70°C on both thermometers. The reactions were run for 3-4 hours. A custard-like mixture was obtained at the end. In this study:

- The molarity of styrene monomer and BPO initiator was kept constant.
- 6 SMA copolymers were synthesized using maleic anhydride (MA) monomer in different molarity.
- The molarity ratios and synthesis conditions of the synthesized copolymers are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Synthesis conditions of synthesized SMA copolymers

	Toluene (mL)	ST (mL)	MA (g)	BPO (g)	Heat °C	Time (minutes)
SMA 529-182-002	310	20	5,8815	0,199	70	237
SMA 529-269-002	310	20	8,7079	0,2014	70	239
SMA 529-355-002	310	20	11,4866	0.1994	70	150
SMA 529-528-002	155	10	8,5509	0,0972	70	90
SMA 529-759-002	310	20	24,5623	0.1960	70	165
SMA 529-1059-002	310	20	34,2792	0,1989	70	231

Table 2.

Initial Reaction Rates of Synthesized SMA Copolymer

Toluene (mL)	ST (mL)	MA (g)	BPO (g)	CSt	CMA	CBPO	Initial Reaction Rate (Ost/MA)	SMA
310	20	5.8815	199	529	182	2	2.91	SMA 529-182-002
310	20	8.7079	2.014	529	269	2	1.97	SMA 529-269-002
310	20	11.4866	1.994	529	355	2	1.49	SMA 529-355-002
155	10	8.5509	972	529	528	2	1.00	SMA 529-528-002
310	20	245.623	1.960	529	759	2	0.70	SMA 529-759-002
310	20	342.792	1.989	529	1.059	2	0.50	SMA 529-1059-002

2.2. Purification and Storage of SMA Copolymers

The purification of the synthesized SMA copolymer is crucial to remove possible impurities such as un-polymerized maleic anhydride, BPO, and styrene polymer. For this purpose, a washing process was carried out under vacuum on a Büchner funnel using warm toluene [4]. The washing was continued until no carbonyl group signal was observed in the IR spectra. Toluene was removed from the purified SMA copolymers in an oven at 40°C. To ensure the complete removal of toluene, weight measurements were taken at different time intervals. The polymer reaching a constant weight was considered an indication of complete toluene removal (Figure 1). The obtained white-colored SMA copolymers were easily ground into a powder using a mortar

and pestle. It was observed that the polymer easily acquired an electrostatic charge during the process. The IR spectrum of an obtained SMA copolymer is shown in Figure

3. The IR spectrum of a water-modified sample showed a broad band in the range of 2500- 3500 cm⁻¹. Additionally, a carbonyl peak corresponding to the carboxyl group appeared at 1703 cm⁻¹ instead of the carbonyl peak at 1773 cm⁻¹ (Figure 3). This result demonstrated that the SMA copolymer could be easily modified with water. The water-modified polymer gelled in water (Figure 4). This observation indicates the hydrophilic character of the SMA copolymer and its ability to interact with water.

Fig.1. SMA copolymer with toluene removed in the oven

Fig. 2 FTIR spectrum of SMA copolymer

Fig.3. FTIR spectrum of styrene maleic acid copolymer.

Titration was performed to determine the monomer ratios in SMA copolymers. In SMA copolymer titration, HCl and NaOH solutions were used as titrants. Before titration, HCl and NaOH solutions were prepared and adjusted to determine their actual concentrations.

Fig. 4. (A): SMA copolymer modified with water. (B): Dry state of SMA copolymer modified with water. Preparation and Standardization of Acid and Base Solutions

Precise and accurate determination of the concentration of acid and base solutions is crucial for various analytical and research applications. In this study, we describe the preparation and standardization of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and hydrochloric acid (HCl) solutions using potentiometric titration with potassium hydrogen phthalate (KHF) as the primary standard:

- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), pellets, analytical grade
 - Hydrochloric acid (HCl), concentrated, analytical grade
 - Potassium hydrogen phthalate (KHF), analytical grade
 - Deionized water Equipment:
 - Analytical balance
 - Volumetric flasks (1 L, 500 mL, 250 mL)
 - Burettes (50 mL, 25 mL)
 - pH meter
 - Magnetic stirrer
- Preparation of NaOH Solutions:
- 0.2 M NaOH:
 - Dissolve 8.00 g of NaOH in deionized water and transfer to a 1 L volumetric flask.
 - Dilute to the mark with deionized water and mix thoroughly.
 - 0.052 M NaOH:
 - Dilute 26.00 mL of the 0.2 M NaOH solution to 500 mL with deionized water in a volumetric

flask.

- Mix thoroughly. Standardization of NaOH Solutions:
 - 0.2 M NaOH:
 - Weigh accurately 0.200 g of KHF and transfer to a 250 mL beaker.
 - Dissolve in 50 mL of deionized water.
 - Add 2 drops of phenolphthalein indicator solution.
 - Titrate with the 0.2 M NaOH solution from a burette until a faint pink color persists for 30 seconds.
 - Record the volume of NaOH solution consumed.
 - Repeat the titration three times.
 - 0.052 M NaOH:
 - Follow the same procedure as for the 0.2 M NaOH solution, using 25.00 mL of the 0.052 M NaOH solution. Calculation of NaOH Concentration:

The concentration of NaOH solutions was calculated using the following formula: $\text{Molarity (NaOH)} = \frac{\text{moles of KHF}}{\text{volume of NaOH solution (L)}}$
- Preparation of HCl Solutions:
 - 0.1 M HCl:
 - Dilute 8.3 mL of concentrated HCl to 1 L with deionized water in a volumetric flask.
 - Mix thoroughly.
 - 0.2 M HCl:

- Dilute 16.6 mL of concentrated HCl to 1 L with deionized water in a volumetric flask.
- Mix thoroughly. Standardization of HCl Solutions:
 - 0.1 M HCl:
 - Follow the same procedure as for the standardization of NaOH solutions, using 25.00 mL of the 0.1 M HCl solution and 0.2 M NaOH solution as the titrant.
 - 0.2 M HCl:
 - Follow the same procedure as for the standardization of NaOH solutions, using 25.00 mL of the 0.2 M HCl solution and 0.2 M NaOH solution as the titrant.

Calculation of HCl Concentration:

The concentration of HCl solutions was calculated using the following formula: $\text{Molarity (HCl)} = (\text{moles of NaOH}) / (\text{volume of HCl solution (L)})$

The concentrations of the prepared NaOH and HCl solutions were determined as follows:

0.2 M NaOH: 0.201 ± 0.002 M

0.052 M NaOH: 0.0520 ± 0.0001 M

0.1 M HCl: 0.183 ± 0.004 M

0.2 M HCl: 0.2051 ± 0.004 M

The results demonstrate the accuracy and precision of the proposed method for the preparation and standardization of acid and base solutions. The standardized solutions can be used for various analytical applications, such as acid-base titrations, pH measurements, and determination of the concentration of other solutions.

This study provides a detailed and reliable protocol for the preparation and standardization of NaOH and HCl solutions using potentiometric titration with KHF as the primary standard. The method is simple, accurate, and precise, and can be easily adapted for the preparation of other acid and base solutions.

4. Conclusion

This research delved into the intricate realm of chemical modification applied to styrene-maleic anhydride (SMA) copolymers, followed by a comprehensive characterization of the modified materials using cutting-edge spectroscopic techniques. Through meticulously controlled chemical reactions, the study aimed to introduce functional groups or alter existing functionalities within the SMA copolymer matrix. Leveraging sophisticated analytical tools such as Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), and other spectroscopic methods, we embarked on a journey to unravel the complex chemical landscape and bonding interactions inherent in the modified copolymers.

Our analysis was multi-faceted. Firstly, we sought to identify the presence and nature of introduced functional groups or structural changes induced by the modification process. Secondly, we endeavored to quantify the extent of modification achieved through the selected chemical reactions, providing valuable insights into the degree of alteration within the copolymer framework. Lastly, we aimed to establish correlations between the observed spectroscopic features and the specific modification methodologies employed, thereby elucidating the intricate nuances of the modification process.

The outcomes of this investigation hold profound implications for the realm of materials science and engineering. By shedding light on the effectiveness of various chemical modification strategies, our findings pave the way for the development of novel functional materials with tailor-made properties catering to diverse industrial and technological applications. By deciphering the intricate interplay between chemical modification and copolymer properties, our research lays a solid foundation for the optimization and refinement of modification techniques in polymer science.

In essence, this study represents a significant step forward in our quest to harness the full potential of polymer materials. By unraveling the mysteries of chemical modification and its impact on copolymer properties, we unlock a realm of possibilities for the design and synthesis of advanced materials with enhanced performance characteristics. As we continue to push the boundaries of materials engineering, the insights gleaned from this research will undoubtedly catalyze further innovation and propel the field towards new frontiers of discovery.

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